

Report D4.7

“Validation of Methodological Framework on Development and Documentation”

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“Validation of Methodological Framework on Development and Documentation”

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
LOT	Linked Open Terms
LOT4OCES	Linked Open Terms Methodology for the OntoCommons Ecosystem
ORSD	Ontology Requirements Specification Document
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

Keywords

Ontology, LOT, LOT4OCES, FAIRness, ORSD

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of validating the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology for ontology development within the OntoCommons project. LOT is a flexible framework with four main phases: Ontology Requirements Specification, Implementation, Publication, and Maintenance. The validation involved surveying users to assess LOT's real-world utility and identify areas for improvement. The survey included five sections covering participants' backgrounds, motivation, and experiences, as well as LOT's core activities. The responses provide valuable feedback. The report highlights key findings and common themes from the analysis of these feedback responses. The report also covers LOT's evolution to align with OntoCommons' ontology stack, leading to the development of Linked Open Terms Methodology for the OntoCommons Ecosystem (LOT4OCES). This specialised version offers a standardised ontology development path. The report briefly describes the specialisations and customisations introduced in LOT4OCES, as well as key discussions and recommendations.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable reports the results of validation of the methodological Framework on ontology development and documentation. Specifically, we focus on the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology as a lightweight framework, drawing from existing methodologies and emphasising alignment with industry needs. Recall that the LOT methodology consists of four main phases covering the whole life cycle of ontology development and documentation: (1) Ontology Requirements Specification: identifying the purpose and requirements of the ontology; (2) Ontology Implementation: building the ontology iteratively based on identified requirements; (3) Ontology Publication: making the ontology accessible online; (4) Ontology Maintenance: updating and improving the ontology as needed.

The validation is carried out mainly by surveying the users of LOT. The main goal is to evaluate the practical usefulness of LOT methodology in real-world scenarios and its impact on ontology development, and the secondary objective is to identify areas for improving the LOT methodology. The survey consists of five sections: the first section collects general information about participants' OntoCommons involvement, motivation for using LOT, and prior experience, and the other four sections align with LOT's core activities: requirements specification, implementation, publication, and maintenance. To perform this survey, OntoCommons demonstrators were emailed and asked to complete the questionnaire within four weeks. The survey aims to assess LOT's real-world usefulness, gather feedback, and includes OntoCommons demonstrators and other participants through various channels. The survey was first presented at the "OntoCommons Second Global Workshop" in June 2023 in Oslo and promoted on social media (Twitter and LinkedIn). It was also emailed to authors mentioning LOT methodology in their papers.

We received a total of seven responses to the questionnaire. These responses provided insightful feedback on the use of the framework and how it can be further improved. In this report, we will provide an extensive overview of the findings we obtained after thoroughly analysing the answers we collected for each question in the questionnaire. The results include a detailed description of the answers provided by the participants, including their responses to open-ended questions and their choices of the closed-ended questions. Additionally, we will highlight any common themes we observed throughout the analysis.

During the course the OntoCommons project, the LOT methodology, known for its flexibility, has been adapted and enhanced to align with OntoCommons' core ontology stack, aiming to improve interoperability across domains. These enhancements have been shaped by input from a diverse community, including industry, academia, consortia, and ongoing projects like EOSC, FAIRsFAIR, and IOF-Core. More specifically, to enhance ontology engineering specificity and rigor, LOT4OCES, named "Linked Open Terms Methodology for the OntoCommons Ecosystem" has been developed. It provides a standardised path for ontology development within the OntoCommons community and

beyond. LOT4OCES contains important specialisations and customisations of LOT, and some key discussions and recommendations are also included in this report.

2. Summary of LOT

One of OntoCommons' goals is to develop a recommendation on the principles, best practices and methods for the development and maintenance of ontologies. For doing so, the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology was described in D4.2 [1] as the methodological framework proposed by OntoCommons as a baseline to be extended and complemented along the project [2]. The LOT methodology provides guidance for the development and documentation of ontologies, including not only guidelines for the activities that should be performed during the ontology development process, but also additional resources, recommendations and tools to support them.

LOT is an overall and lightweight methodology to build ontologies based on existing methodologies such as NeOn [3], Grüninger & Fox [4], METHONTOLOGY [5] and oriented towards developments and technologies in the semantic web. The LOT methodology focuses on alignment with industrial development, in addition to academic and research projects and software development.

As it can be observed in , the LOT methodology is structured in four main phases, namely:

Ontology requirements specification: The aim of the requirements specification process is to state why the ontology is being built and to identify and define the requirements the ontology should fulfil. Taking as input the documentation and data provided by domain experts and users, the ontology development team generates a first proposal of ontological requirements written in the form of competency questions or statements. In this step, involvement and commitment by experts in the specific domain at hand is required to generate the appropriate industry perspective and knowledge.

Ontology implementation: The aim of the ontology implementation process is to build the ontology using a formal language, based on the ontological requirements identified by the domain experts. After defining the first set of requirements, though modification and addition of requirements is allowed during the development, the ontology implementation phase is carried out through a number of sprints. The ontology development team builds the ontology iteratively, implementing only a certain number of requirements in each iteration. The output of each iteration is a new version of the ontology.

Ontology publication: The aim of the ontology publication process is to provide an online ontology accessible both as a human-readable documentation and a machine-readable file from its URI.

Ontology maintenance: The goal of this activity is to update and add new requirements to the ontology that are not identified in the Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSD), to identify and correct errors or to schedule a new iteration for ontology development. During the

ontology development process, the domain experts can propose new requirements or improvements over the ontology, as well as identify errors both in the requirements and in the implementation.

Figure 1: LOT Methodology Phases

3. Background on Demonstrators

The evaluation of the LOT methodology is based on the demonstrators related to OntoCommons. The demonstrators are a list of use cases that are used to provide the effectiveness of the LOT methodology and provide insights on the use of the methodology.

OAS, a highly agile company with a strong national and international market presence, is increasingly focusing on product customisation and the provision of services related to its products, such as developing Product Service Systems (PSS). Recognising the need to expand its systems into Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), OAS aims to incorporate product and process optimisation as an integral component of their tailored turn-key PSS solutions.

Bosh Group, a renowned global provider of technology and services, faces the challenge of automating manufacturing processes, including microchip production at the Bosch Salzgitter factory. This requires the monitoring, analysis, and control of various processes and machinery, necessitating the integration of diverse data sets. These datasets range from sensor data generated by machines to process specifications and legacy SAP data. Bosch addresses this challenge, in part, by developing a unified Industry information model in the form of an ontology.

Tekniker, a specialised technology centre, focuses on advanced manufacturing, surface engineering, product engineering, and ICTs for manufacturing. They maintain the Tribology Characterisation Demonstrator (TRIBONT) ontology, which supports the engineering process for developing new products and finding sustainable solutions through innovative materials.

A research student at Cardiff University, maintains the Forest Observatory Ontology (FOO). FOO serves as a descriptive framework for wildlife data collected via remote sensing devices.

The CASO and IRRIG ontologies were developed in 2018 by the research unit Technologies and Information Systems for Agricultural System (TSCF), located at Irstea centre of Clermont-Ferrand. The Context-Aware System Ontology (CASO) and Irrigation ontology (IRRIG) were developed to support context aware system for the smart irrigation use case.

4. Methodology

4.1 Survey Objectives

The main objective of the survey is to determine which parts of the LOT methodology are helpful in the context of concrete use-case scenarios and to what extent the adoption of the LOT methodology impacts both ontology engineering work-flows as well as created artefacts, e.g., ontologies. A secondary objective of the survey is to identify potential points for improvement of the LOT methodology.

4.2 Material

The used questionnaire consists of five parts. The first part is about general information regarding the participant's involvement in OntoCommons, their motivation for using the LOT methodology as well as background information about available LOT materials and prior training experience. The other four parts correspond to the four different main phases in LOT, namely, requirements specification, implementation, publication, and maintenance. More precisely, each section asked for specific details about how the activities described in LOT methodology for each phase were carried out in each use case.

4.3 Procedure

Demonstrator associated with the OntoCommons project were approached by email and asked to provide a report of their experience with LOT and fill out the questionnaire mentioned above. They were provided with a link to an online form to the questionnaire described in <https://short.upm.es/lgm17>. Participants were given four weeks to do so.

Apart from requesting OntoCommons demonstrators to fill in the survey, it has been shared during "OntoCommons Second Global Workshop" that took place in Oslo from the 13th to the 16th of June, 2023, and online. The survey has also been promoted via social media posts (Twitter and LinkedIn)

and by email to ontology authors that notified the use of the methodology in conference or journal papers.

5. Results

We received a total of seven responses from OntoCommons demonstrators and ontology developers who have implemented the OntoCommons methodological framework in their projects. These responses provided insightful feedback on the use of the framework and how it can be further improved.

In the upcoming sections, we will provide an extensive overview of the findings we obtained after thoroughly analysing the answers we collected for each question in the questionnaire. The results that we will present include a detailed description of the answers provided by the participants, including their responses to open-ended questions and their choices of the closed-ended questions. Additionally, we will highlight any common themes we observed throughout the analysis.

5.1 Context in OntoCommons

The methodological framework has been proved to be highly effective in developing ontologies in various contexts both within and outside OntoCommons. Within the OntoCommons community, this framework has been utilised to develop the resistance spot welding ontology, part of the product service system ontology (for documenting Yard Management ecosystem data specifically), the TRIBONT ontology, and the core ontology of a tool managing and exploiting tribological characterisation information. Moreover, outside of the OntoCommons community, it has been applied in the development of ontologies for a wide array of application and data integration systems. These use cases have been presented in numerous OntoCommons Workshops, ESWC conferences, and other dissemination venues, which have helped to further showcase the versatility and effectiveness of this methodological framework.

There are several reasons why the responders chose to use the methodological framework. First, using the framework provides several benefits, such as the ability to work in a standardised way, ensuring that the ontology meets user requirements, and promoting reuse. Additionally, the framework is agile, lightweight, well-maintained, and has many supported resources. In some specific cases, the framework was chosen because it best suited the use case for a PhD research project. As an OntoCommons demonstrator, the adoption of LOT methodology was also a natural fit. However, not all demonstrators started their work using the LOT methodology. One of the demonstrator pointed out that they altered to LOT methodology for further development and application of their previous ontology.

5.2 LOT training & LOT materials

In terms of whether the participants received comprehensive training on implementing the proposed methodological framework, the results seem to be divided. Half of the participants reported that they did not receive any formal training, but instead had to rely on available documentation, analyse how other projects had adopted the framework, or read relevant publications on the topic. On the other hand, the remaining half reported having received some training on certain aspects of the methodology, such as the different phases in the framework (e.g., ontology validation) and the languages used to operate the tools under the framework. It is worth noting that while some participants received training, it is unclear whether this was sufficient to fully grasp the method of the proposed framework and implement it effectively in their project.

Many of the responders have expressed that they are able to find useful material online. One of the most helpful resources mentioned by the responders is the website for the methodological framework: <https://lot.linkeddata.es/>. In addition, some of the responders also mentioned that they found useful material through publications, such as academic journals and research papers.

5.3 LOT phases used by Demonstrators

The methodological framework included four key phases: Ontology Requirements Specification, Ontology Implementation, Ontology Publication, and Ontology Maintenance. Each of these phases played a critical role in ensuring that the ontologies we created met the needs of the diverse range of users. During the course of our investigation, we discovered that all of the phases had been utilised throughout the entire development process of the ontologies. However, some projects have not reached the phases of Ontology Publication and Ontology Maintenance yet. Therefore, only the first two phases have been adopted.

In the upcoming section, we will further analyse the phases by breaking them down into specific activities and scrutinising each of them. By doing so, we will be able to comprehensively assess the efficiency and effectiveness of the methodological framework for the benefit of the users. Additionally, we will examine how each of the phases and activities could be optimised to enhance the overall user experience and achieve higher levels of success. This level of detail will provide a more holistic understanding of the methodology and its practical applications.

5.4 LOT activities

5.4.1 Use Case Specification

The LOT methodology provides some examples of use cases consisting of information such as textual description, actor, and flow. However, the methodology does not provide a specific template on

required information to be collected as part of use case specification. Most of the use cases provide a high level mission and vision of their project which focus on the application or use of the data. It is very important for the domain expert and ontology engineers to interview users to extract more information on the data related activities. A list of standard questionnaire will be helpful for domain experts and ontology engineers to curate necessary information as part of use case specification. In OntoCommons, demonstrators were surveyed with a form asking questions on not only the description, actors, and flow, but also pre-condition and post-condition of their scenario, data sources, relevant vocabulary, technology readiness level, and KPIs. Descriptions of use cases could be found in D5.2 [6]. It is observed that user representative may not always be aware of the data specification practical scenario. Domain experts should make effort in interpreting the data requirements from use case descriptions. For this purpose, flow charts, system diagram, and ER diagram supplied by users may be helpful. Moreover, the use case may require other developments in the systems and software apart from the ontology. It is a responsibility of domain expert and ontology engineers to delineate the ontology development through a two-way dialogue with the users to correctly identify the scope of the work regarding ontology development and document the same in the use case specification.

As observed in our survey, for the continuation of earlier projects on Ontology development in the same organisation, users may want to reuse parts of those developments. Such information regarding existing ontology related to the use case, technological infrastructure, software, and various other learnings and pitfalls also need to include in the use case specification. In the end, the use case specification should include the improvements or achievements expected by in terms of quantifiable measures, e.g., KPIs and TRLs.

5.4.2 Data Exchange Identification

In this phase the documentation is collected on: datasets, regulations, standards, data formats, APIs specifications, database schemas, etc. Although LOT workflow mentions this step as a complimentary step, in our past experiences and the survey of other projects, the difficulties in acquiring these information are observed. Companies are not always ready to share confidential data or API specifications. The users also may not be aware of the database schema deep inside the back end infrastructure or because of the obscurity imposed by the systems customer is using. Additionally, a description of various data models and API specification need to be understood unambiguously as the former are often data centric and the latter is more application centric. Many of these problems may be mitigated by adopting a FAIR data principles to describe the data as FAIR metadata not only describe the data but also provide some level of assurance to the customers on the privacy and security of their data.

5.4.3 *Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSD)*

Once the ontology development team has all the information about the requirements, obtained from the “purpose and scope identification”, “ontological requirements proposal” and “ontological requirements completion” activities, the Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSD) is created. This specification document stores all the functional and non-functional requirements identified and the information associated to them. In our past experiences and the survey conducted on LOT adopters, ORSD is a proven way to document ontology requirements.

The purpose and scope fields need to clearly delineate the work to be carried out in the ontology front. Therefore these two statements are required to be extracted from the broad use case specification as mentioned in Sec. 4.4.1, users may need to be involved in this phase providing review and final approval as an agreement on the intended coverage of the work.

Another important section that is often overlooked is the “intended use”. This section may be adopted for describing the use case, the systems and their components (including associated diagrams and charts), data flows, and user and system interactions which are to be impacted by the ontology development. As there is no specific section to provide the user story, this section may also be adopted for providing one, if available.

The non-functional requirement section is generally used to capture information on existing ontology or standards to be reused, instruction on metadata and multi-lingual support. Several other concerns regarding ontology development may also be mentioned if given by the customers. These include IRI structure, encoding formats, expressivity of the language and recommended reasoners to be used, various evaluation criteria, documentation and publication strategies as well as code development infrastructure, e.g., code repository, issue and bug management tool, integration and deployment tool etc. If these information are not available from the client then they need to be decided during implementation phase by the ontology engineers by understanding the client’s situation through discussions and negotiations.

Although pre-glossary terms are mentioned as optional by LOT, especially in case of functional requirements captured in concept table, we found its importance in most of the projects. Coming up a glossary from CQs and answers is particularly important in large projects for prioritising the work based on importance derived from the frequency of the terms. However, ORSD does not specifically mention a format for creating such glossary. A standardised template for this purpose is necessary.

5.4.4 Functional Ontology requirements Formalisation

Although LOT mentions three alternative methods to write functional requirements for the ontology, competency questions are most popular method. This is evident from the work of OntoCommons demonstrators surveyed. However, CQs are often written in a way that is easier to be converted to SPARQL, making them only looking for explicitly asserted information from the knowledge base. This is often a weak use of CQs. For more effective use of CQ in the evaluation, it is important to form CQs in a way that requires implicit information that to be inferred by the axioms or rules in the ontology. It is also needs to be remembered that many other forms of query and validation tools except SPARQL, e.g, SQWRL, SHACL, and DL Query may be used evaluating the CQs in the testing phase. This makes writing CQs the most crucial as well as difficult part of the ontology requirement specification.

Coming up with quality CQs requires concerted effort from ontology engineers, users and domain experts. It is also a responsibility of the ontology engineers to educate the users to read and interpret CQs to ensure their involvement and help them to review CQs according to completion criteria. Another way to mitigate the challenge is to write the CQs in two phases: 1) informal CQs to be written by users with the help of ontology engineers and domain experts and 2) formal CQs to be developed by ontology engineers by rewriting the informal CQs with formal terminologies.

The template for writing CQs from Vicinity project, available as part of LOT resources is an useful template to be used, however we found different projects using their own template or writing them directly in the Functional Requirement section of ORSD template.

The CQs need to evaluated for completion by applying a list of criteria e.g., completeness, correctness, consistency, verifiability, comprehensibility, unambiguity, conciseness. Some of these criteria may be difficult to assess as par our experience from last projects, and requirement engineering for OntoCommons demonstrators. Some of these difficulties are mentioned in Section 5 of D3.3 [7]. In summary, the criteria are difficult to apply for domain ontology reference or upper level ontology development. If the scope of the work is not defined, some of the criteria will be difficult to apply. The judgement is often subjective therefore it requires to involve multiple sources to truth, engaging multiple representatives from both users and ontology engineers.

5.4.5 Ontology Implementation

Figure 2 shows the ontology implementation sub-activities within the LOT methodology. The responses to the questionnaire brought insights about to which extent the suggested steps of the LOT methodology were followed for the ontology implementation activity.

Figure 2: Ontology Implementation Sub-activities

5.4.6 Ontology Conceptualisation

The LOT methodology recommends to use diagrams (e.g., based on UML) to graphically design the ontology conceptualisation. An initial conceptualisation in the form of a diagram seems indeed to be a good practice among the interviewed demonstrators, as 6 out of 7 use some sort of diagram before moving to the ontology encoding. Chowlk notation is used in three of the use cases, hence facilitating the automatic transformation of the diagram into an initial OWL encoding. Custom diagrams using draw.io are also used in two cases. UML is the preferred choice in one of the cases. Finally, only one of the cases does not specify the type of diagrams used for the conceptualisation.

5.4.7 Ontology Encoding

The purpose of the encoding activity is to implement the ontology in a formal language, following FAIR principles in addition to the formalisation. The selected formal modelling language in all 7 use cases was the OWL ontology language. In two of the use cases OWL was also extended with Semantic Web Rule Language (SWRL).

The responses do not provide information about the followed practices to achieve FAIRness when sharing the ontology (e.g., metadata). Upon inspecting two of the public ontologies, metadata at the level of the ontology and version number of the ontology is provided according to the LOT

methodology. Although most of the entities included labels, additional metadata at the level of the entities seems to be missing.

The LOT methodology could be more precise in terms of the expected annotations for an ontology and a term, possibly by providing the vocabulary of the annotation properties to be used.

5.4.8 Ontology Reuse

Ontology reuse is a common practice and in all seven use cases there was some kind of ontology reuse. The responses, however, provide little detail about the type of reuse with respect to the LOT guidelines (e.g., hard or soft reuse).

The inspection of two of the ontologies from the use cases, however, do not provide much clarity as they do not include any import statement nor references to external entities (i.e. entities with external URIs). It seems the reused knowledge has been embedded with the ontologies. The LOT methodology could also emphasise in this activity (in addition to the ontology implementation), as a good practice, to keep the provenance to the original reused knowledge.

Another of the use cases, justifies the creation of a new ontology in terms of aimed quality. The new ontology is then aligned to the existing state-of-the-art ontologies.

The use cases also lack concrete description about the reused Ontology Design Patterns. The LOT methodology could be more specific in this point as ODP may be unknown to the domain experts/ontology developers.

5.4.9 Ontology Evaluation

The LOT methodology suggests different dimensions to evaluate an ontology. Only two use cases did not have an evaluation in place yet. The most common evaluation techniques (4 out of 7) were the use of the Ontology Pitfall Scanner (OOPS, <https://oops.linkeddata.es/index.jsp>) and its extension Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR (FOOPS, https://foops.linkeddata.es/FAIR_validator.html). In two use cases consistency via reasoning was also considered. Modularity is also taken into account in two cases. The execution of SPARQL queries as part of the evaluation is also done in two cases. Git error reporting is also taken into account as part of the evaluation in one of the use cases.

The LOT methodology, as highlighted in one of the points above, could be more specific in terms of suggested applications like OOPS and state-of-the-art reasoning engines to check for consistency.

5.4.10 Documentation Generation

The aim of the ontology documentation generation is to provide a human-readable documentation for the developed ontology. All of the feedback confirms that they are either working on (2 out of 7) the generation of the documentation, or already published (5 out of 7) the ontologies. A small number of answers (2 out of 7) mention that they are using w3id.org namespace as the prefix for

their ontology IRIs. Most of the respondents (5 out of 7) use the Widoco (<https://github.com/dgarijo/Widoco>) for documenting the ontologies, and two of them are also using the OnTooLogy tool (<https://ontology.linkeddata.es/>).

5.4.11 Online Publication

The aim of the ontology publication process is to provide an online ontology accessible both as a human-readable documentation and a machine-readable file from its URI. All the publicly available ontologies (4 out of 7) are published using Github pages with the domain github.io. Two answers mentioned the usage of industry portal. Two answers included also the published formats: HTML and OWL/RDF/TTL.

5.4.12 Bug Detection

The purpose of bug detection is to identify errors both in the requirements and in the implementation. All the answers report that they are relying on Github issues to manage the bugs.

5.4.13 New Requirements Proposal

The goal of this activity is to update and add new requirements to the ontology that are not identified in the previous steps. During the ontology development process, the domain experts can propose new requirements or improvements over the ontology. Almost all the answers (6 out of 7) report that they are relying on Github issues to collect proposal. Some (2 out of 7) also use email contact. Only one said they don't provide this functionality.

6. Discussion

As shown in the data gathered through the survey the LOT methodology is well organised and the steps are comprehensible for users. In addition, the resources provided in the website are proven to be useful.

As possible improvements of the methodology we can mention:

- Provide more guidelines for FAIR ontology sharing and propose minimum metadata fields. This action point could be also implemented by providing a template for metadata as part of the Chowlk notation templates.
- Include guidelines about how to document provenance about the reused ontologies when no owl: import is used.
- Provide more information about Ontology Design Patterns definitions, reuse and related tools or resources.

It should be mentioned that some answers pointed out a lack of references for ontology evaluation tools, however, it seems to be due to the fact that some users might have follow only the LOT website instead of the research paper that contains pointers to guidelines, resources and tools for all activities. This issue could be addressed by including more links to the open access paper in the methodology website (note: this action has already been implemented) and adding more links to the available resources.

7. Developments (Methods, Tools, Resources)

During the course of the OntoCommons project, various developments were undertaken both on the improvement of the de-facto LOT methodology and supporting its workflow by appropriate tools. The developments regarding methodology is presented in Section 7.1 and the development regarding tools is presented in Section 7.2.

7.1 Developments on ontology engineering methodology

The LOT methodology serves as a versatile framework for ontology development. It has been extensively utilised within OntoCommons, showcasing its adaptability by allowing users to tailor the methodology to their specific needs. This flexibility, while advantageous, has also introduced challenges, leading to variations in ontology quality, encoding styles, and metadata. Consequently, this diversity hampers seamless interoperability among ontologies. To address this issue, a more specialised approach is necessary, specifically, aligning with the core ontology stack that has been proposed and developed by OntoCommons to serve as the crux of OntoCommons Ecosystem (OCES) for achieving interoperability across domains.

Throughout OntoCommons' journey, numerous enhancements have been introduced, including tools, templates, and guidelines spanning requirement engineering, ontology development, ontology evaluation, and the promotion of ontology FAIRness. These improvements have been thoughtfully shaped by input from a diverse community, including industry, academia, and consortia, as well as ongoing projects such as EOSC, FAIRsFAIR, IOF-Core, among others.

To enhance the specificity and rigor of ontology engineering, the LOT methodology's specialisation must encompass these developments. Importantly, this evolution retains the original flow and critical steps of the LOT methodology. In this regard, OntoCommons has meticulously crafted a normative guide for ontology engineering, aptly named LOT4OCES – Linked Open Terms Methodology for the OntoCommons Ecosystem. This comprehensive guide serves as a beacon for practitioners, offering a precise and standardised path for ontology development within the OntoCommons community and beyond.

While the complete guide LOT4OCES is not included in this report, the following sections discuss some of the important specialisations and customisations included in the LOT4OCES. Along with the motivations for each specialisation, several recommendations addressed by LOT4OCES are also presented.

1) Customisation to general workflow

- a) In the requirement phase, LOT methodology includes the activity: “Functional ontology requirement formalisation” as an optional activity. In this phase, the informal competency questions formulated in “Functional ontology requirement proposal” are rephrased in terms of test query, e.g., SPARQL, and expected answers which can be executed over the ontology to verify if the ontology satisfies the ontological requirements identified later in the ontology development process, more precisely during the ontology evaluation. However, it is not possible to formulate the test queries from informal competency questions at this point of “Ontology requirement specification” phase as the terms to be used in those queries are only available during “Ontology implementation” phase. Although in some cases these terms can be derived from existing ontologies, it is expected that most of the development and update of ontology will require several new terms to be defined in the ontology only in the implementation phase. This will require LOT4OCES to define a revisit from “Ontology implementation” phase to “Ontology requirement specification” phase and back. Instead, LOT4OCES moves the activity “Functional ontology requirement formalisation” before the “Ontology evaluation” activity in “Ontology implementation” phase.
- b) “Ontology evaluation” activity includes tasks for verification and validation of the ontology. However, the ontology also needs to be evaluated for its FAIRness. However, evaluation of the FAIRness of the ontology could only be completed after the ontology is published. This is because many FAIR principles require permanent URIs, and other metadata curated in the repository where the ontology is hosted. A new activity is added after the “Ontology

publication” phase called “Ontology FAIRness evaluation”. Furthermore, “Ontology evaluation report” is added as an output of the “Ontology evaluation” along with the “Evaluated ontology”. The output of “Ontology FAIRness evaluation” also points to “Ontology evaluation report” indicating that FAIRness of the ontology requires to be evaluated to complete the evaluation of the ontology.

- 2) LOT classifies the roles involved in ontology development into three categories: ontology developer, domain expert, and ontology user. Different ontology development projects additionally mention many other roles. Aiming to harmonise these roles under these three categories, LOT4OCES classifies and reassigns them to different activities in Table 1 (Appendix B). Additionally, two more roles are identified: ontology curator, who is not part of the core development team but may help the team to publish ontology in a repository regarding metadata and FAIRness assurance, and data modeller, who is involved in the “Ontology exploitation” phase (see D4.6[8]). However, in a practical project, same person can play multiple roles.
- 3) Ontology requirement specification:
 - c) The ontology development team is required to perform a series of interviews with the product owner and other users to gather Use cases and Data sets. A successful collection of use cases and data sets is vital for writing the ontology requirement specifications successfully. For this reason, a set of questions in the form of a template, given in Table 2 (Appendix B), is recommended to be used by the ontology analyst to write the use cases. This template is used by OntoCommons to collect the details of demonstrators' use cases that are further used in formulating the ontology requirements.
 - d) Similarly, Ontology analysts are required to analyze the data for extracting potential features and the relationships among them in consultation with the domain expert and product owner. Different types of data require different entities to be documented, for example,
 - i) For a set of APIs, the JSON data model, the API specification document and a sample of API requests and responses need to be documented.
 - ii) For relational data in database tables, the schema for tables, fields, relationships and viewed may be documented along with constraints using both primary and foreign keys.
 - iii) For comma-separated, tab-separated files, and spreadsheets (common for logs, and records) the fields may be documented as well and more persistent storage of the record, possibly in some databases may be investigated for more information.
 - iv) For unstructured data, e.g., free text, images, and audio, common metadata for the data files may be collected. Exploring the unstructured data requires further processing. These techniques are out of the purview of this guide.

In Table 3 (Appendix B), a general template is recommended for collecting important information regarding the data.

- e) Competency questions being the most popular method of encoding functional requirements for ontology, LOT4OCES recommends several best practices for writing competency questions. Although LOT4OCES does not prohibit the use of natural language statements or tabular information, it also does not include them in the guide, indicating the competency question is a preferred method. The method of formulating effective competency questions is also prescribed by LOT4OCES as well as a template, which strongly follows the Vicinity template proposed by LOT. However, a couple of new fields are added to the template to support complex competency questions to address such needs arising from the application of this template by OntoCommons in the requirement collection activities. This template is given in Table 4 (Appendix B).
- f) The completion criteria recommended by LOT to test the validity and completion of the competency questions as part of “Functional ontology requirement completion” activity is reformulated to narrow the scope and target of the criteria. The reformulation aims to provide a solution to the difficulty in applying the criteria as observed in T3.3. The reformulated completion criteria are given below:
 - i) A set of competency questions is correct if each competency question is about some aspect of a user story that needs to be modelled by the ontology.
 - ii) A set of competency questions is complete if no additional competency question is required to be added to the set, i.e., there are no user stories which has some aspect that is not covered by the competency questions.
 - iii) A set of competency questions is internally consistent if no conflicts exist between them, i.e., for every competency question, the assumption of correctness of its answer should not imply the answer to any other competency question is incorrect.
 - iv) A set of competency questions is verifiable if there is a finite process with a reasonable cost that tests whether the final ontology satisfies each requirement, i.e., there should not be any competency question which requires access to additional data (not associated with the user story the competency question is about), manual interventions, or execution of algorithms to derive the answer.
 - v) A set of competency questions is comprehensible if every competency question is understandable to the product owner and the ontology analyst.
 - vi) A set of competency questions is unambiguous if every competency question has only one possible answer for every situation.
 - vii) A set of competency questions is concise if every competency question is relevant, i.e., no duplicated or irrelevant competency question exists in the set.

g) LOT4OCES recommends the development of pre-glossary terms as an important step while it is an optional step for LOT. This is because pre-glossary terms help in making several important decisions in the subsequent phases, for example, identifying the priority and important concepts, finding suitable existing ontology to reuse, and conceptualising the ontology based on the correct context. LOT4OCES also prescribes a correct way to prepare the pre-glossary terms by recommending a table for this purpose, as shown in Table 5 (Appendix B).

4) Ontology implementation

h) In addition to the guidelines from LOT methodology, LOT4OCES puts strong emphasis on the reuse of OCES ontology stack, the use of pre-glossary terms, and building semantically rich definitions of terms in the ontology implementation phase. These considerations impact some specialised steps in the “Ontology conceptualisation” and “Ontology implementation” activities. In this report, these specialisations are briefly mentioned.

- i) Required classes and properties to be included in the ontology need to be identified from the pre-glossary terms and their use in the corresponding competency questions.
- ii) Every class and property need to be described by a formal definition. A formal definition should follow all best practices of writing definition and can be of the form of either a necessary condition, sufficient condition or necessary and jointly sufficient condition. To determine these conditions ontologists may analyse the traits of the concept that the term represents. In this effort, relevant domain references, standards, and input from domain experts and ontology analysts are considered.
- iii) Existing ontologies that can provide terms as the supertypes (parent classes or properties) of the new terms are to be identified from existing ontology repositories (IndustryPortal for industrial domains and Matportal for materials science, but also LOV, Agroportal, Bioportal etc.). Additionally, these ontologies are highly recommended to be part of the OCES ontology stack, i.e., the ontology is recursively mapped to one of the top-level ontologies that are part of Top Reference Ontology (TRO). It is also possible to reuse terms from ontologies that are not mapped to some ontology from the OCES ontology stack, but it is highly recommended that they are to be first mapped to some top or mid-level ontology or one of the bridge concepts from the OCES ontology stack. Following these recommendations is critical for ensuring the interoperability of the ontology being developed.
- iv) A template for conceptualising the terms (classes or properties), given in Table 6 (Appendix B), is suggested by LOT4OCES. This template helps in collecting domain references and input from stakeholders, analyzing the traits, building definitions, and building mapping to existing terms from other ontologies.

- v) A separate set of best practices is also provided by LOT4OCES for writing effective definitions of the terms. These best practices include Aristotelian definition pattern (genus and differentia), avoiding nominals, plurals, circularity, abbreviation, and use-mention distinction, among others.
- i) LOT4OCES provides a detailed guide on ontology encoding regarding the IRI convention, versioning, naming convention, annotations, language, and expressivity. While recommending these best practices, LOT4OCES refers to Ontology Technical Principles (part of D2.9 [9]) where these best practices are detailed. These specialisations are not included in this report but mention some of the key takeaways below.
 - i) IRI and naming conventions recommend the IRI grammar, choice of host and paths, conventions over hash vs. slash and strategies for permanent URLs.
 - ii) Naming conventions recommend how the terms of the ontology should be labelled and convention over opaque and transparent IRI.
 - iii) Annotations and metadata recommend the set of annotation properties to be used in documenting terms in the ontology, best practices for effectively providing their values, as well as metadata to be used to annotate the ontology.
 - iv) The versioning scheme recommends how to maintain and manage versions of the ontology, conventions for version IRI and other metadata to be assigned for change management.
 - v) Expressivity and reasoners guide recommends a strategy to select the most suitable expressivity level for the ontology language, best practices for different OWL profiles, and corresponding choices of reasoners.
 - vi) Mapping relation vocabulary recommends best practices to map concepts among ontologies and the metadata to be used to annotate them.
 - vii) Serialisation format recommends the strategy of choosing the correct serialisation format based on different trade-offs.
- j) LOT4OCES recommends a separate ontology evaluation guide for testing the ontology rigorously. A set of questionnaires is prepared to guide the evaluation process. This template is under development at the time of writing this report. Due to brevity, the template is not included in this report. This template is supported by detailed methods of how to evaluate the ontology for each aspect mentioned in the questions. LOT4OCES recommends Three types of primary evaluations: structural (only based on the ontology source file, without knowing the requirement or scope), which is classified as validation as per LOT, functional (against the functional requirement) which is classified as verification as per LOT, FAIRness (which can be completely performed after the ontology is released but some aspects in reusability and interoperability may be evaluated at this stage). Not all evaluations can be

performed automatically, therefore, LOT4OCES highly recommends peer review by ontologists, logicians, ontology analysts and domain experts to evaluate many aspects of the ontology.

5) Ontology publication

- k) Formalising data documentation is an important aspect of OntoCommons. It is the process of recording all relevant aspects of data to make it FAIR and facilitate its use and exploitation. It is possible to categorise data documentation into four distinct, but interconnected levels as shown in **Error! Reference source not found..**

Figure 3: The four levels of data documentation. While cataloguing is an essential step for making data available for management and exploitation, the other three levels enrich the data documentation semantically and makes it much more interoperable and reusable

Cataloguing provides a standardised way of describing and indexing data resources, making them easier for users to locate and utilise. It should provide sufficient information about where the data is located, the protocols used to access the data, needed authentication and authorisation procedures, etc. to make it accessible. In addition, data catalogues also include standardised metadata, such as title, keywords, license, owner, project, contact person, format, etc. enabling basic keyword-based search.

Structural data documentation describes how data is structured and represented numerically. It is an essential step for going from compatibility to interoperability. By standardising the description of the data representation, it becomes easier to combine and integrate data from various sources and make it more easily accessible to a broader range of users. The DataModel Ontology [10], provides a representation for data models that can help to ensure interoperability across different applications and contexts. This ontology is a simple yet comprehensive representation of the data, designed to be feature complete and easy to use.

Contextual data documentation is about providing sufficient context to the data to make it reusable. This is typically done by relating or linking the data items to other data items (aka linked data) in a knowledge base. For example, consider a dataset consisting of results from

tensile tests from a series of welded joints between aluminium and steel. Obvious context that would be needed for most reuse of this dataset is to relate it to other datasets for the geometry of the welded sample from where the sample is taken, the composition and temper of the aluminium, steel and filler materials, type of welding and welding parameters, etc. Additional useful context to this dataset would e.g. be references to related datasets for the same sample, like TEM characterisation of the intermetallic phases that formed at different distances from the centre of the welding zone. All such metadata can be expressed with RDF triples in a knowledge base, resulting in a rich graph of linked data. In addition to reusability, contextual documentation also enables data exploration and semantic search.

Semantic data documentation expresses the shared meaning of the data by mapping it to concepts in published ontologies, that are typically uniquely identified with IRIs. The logical structure of ontologies enhances the contextual data documentation by allowing the user to infer new relations between data items. Semantic data documentation enables unambiguously exchange of knowledge and thereby cross-disciplinary and semantic interoperability. It also allows for advanced data exploration by exploiting the logical structure of the underlying ontologies.

Today, many data documentation systems only include cataloguing, limiting the use of their data to compatible systems or requiring human significant intervention and effort to use their data. To increase the level of FAIRness and address the need for cross-disciplinarity and semantic interoperability all levels of data documentation are required, supported by an ecosystem of ontologies and semantic tools.

LOT4OCES provides a special guideline on publishing the ontology stressing the maintenance of FAIR principles while publishing. Although ontology artefacts may be registered in many FAIR data repositories, LOT4OCES highly recommends publishing the ontology in a dedicated ontology repository, e.g., IndustryPortal, for industrial ontology, and Matportal for material science ontology in addition to general purpose repositories. These ontology repositories, especially IndustryPortal provide many additional functionalities to maintain the versions of the source file, mappings among ontologies, and services to promote the exploitation of the ontologies in the repository, along with a detailed provision of FAIR metadata and FAIRness evaluator. A profile of minimum metadata for ontologies is a highly debated and ongoing study in the FAIR community, still, LOT4OCES recommends MOD (Industryportal currently supports version 1.4) metadata profile being the most comprehensive metadata profile, for the time being until a more conclusive profile is decided. LOT4OCES recommends that ontologies should be published with good-quality metadata to the extent that the integrated FAIR evaluator can score the artefact to be FAIR (at least 240 credits by O'Faire). The evaluation of FAIRness in turn completes the evaluation of the ontology. It also mentions a

special role called Ontology curator, a specialist in registering the ontology in the repository and assuring FAIRness, to guide and support ontology developers in this task.

7.2 Developments on tools

Among many tools developed in the course of OntoCommons, only some of the tools, which have an impact on the entire methodology of ontology engineering, are enlisted below.

- 1) LOT4OCES also provides a one-stop-shop alike system for orchestrating ontology development activities available at <https://tooling.ontocommons.linkeddata.es/> depicted in Figure 4. This web application allows uploading one or more ontologies and execute a number of tools over the ontologies. More precisely, the tools available are Widoco (<https://dgarigo.github.io/Widoco/>) for ontology documentation, OOPS (<https://oops.linkeddata.es/>) and Themis (<http://themis.linkeddata.es/>) for ontology evaluation and Astrea (<https://astrea.linkeddata.es/>) for Shapes generation. the pipeline could be executed over OWL files or could be triggered by ontology conceptualisations following the Chowlk notation, in which case the Chowlk converter will be executed in order to obtain an OWL ontology to be used as input for the rest of tools. This system also provide links to main ontology registries to look for ontologies or to registered the ontology being built as well to links to best practices and recommendations for publishing FAIR vocabularies.

Figure 4: LOT4OCES ontology development tooling

- 2) During the course of the OntoCommons project, the ontology ecosystem knowledge graph was developed with the aim of capturing and organising all the information related to the project's methodological and technological support [11], [12]. This unique resource goes beyond existing tools in the field by encoding machine-readable data that describes not only the methodological framework and reference implementation, but also the relationships between different concepts within the ontology ecosystem. By doing so, it provides a more comprehensive and interconnected view of the ontology commons ecosystem toolkit, enabling researchers and practitioners to more easily navigate and utilise the wealth of knowledge available in OntoCommons. To access the knowledge graph online, users should log in using the following account credentials: username: viewer, password: viewer, for OCEANS, or download the ontology ecosystem knowledge graph from its GitHub repository.

- 3) EMMOntoPy is a Python package based on the excellent Owlready2 package, which provides a natural and intuitive representation of ontologies in Python [13]. EMMOntoPy extends Owlready2 and adds additional functionality, like accessing entities by label, reasoning with FaCT++ and parsing logical expressions in Manchester syntax. It also include a set of tools, like creating an ontology from an Excel sheet, generation of reference documentation of ontologies and visualisation of ontologies graphically. EMMOntoPy is freely available for on <https://github.com/emmo-repo/EMMOntoPy/> and on PyPI under the permissive open source BSD 3-Clause license (<https://github.com/emmo-repo/EMMOntoPy/>). EMMOntoPy was originally developed to work effectively with Elemental Multiperspective Material Ontology (EMMO) and EMMO-based domain ontologies. Owlready2, and thereby also EMMOntoPy, represents OWL classes and individuals in Python as classes and instances. OWL properties are represented as Python attributes. Hence, it provides a new dot notation for representing ontologies as valid Python code. The notation is simple and easy to understand and write for people with some knowledge of OWL and Python. Since Python is a versatile programming language, Owlready2 does not only allow for representation of OWL ontologies, but also to work with them programmatically, including interpretation, modification and generation. EMMOntoPy is a layer on top of Owlready2, that provides that provides a range of additional features. Some of the additional features provided by EMMOntoPy are listed below: Access by label, Turtle serialisation/deserialisation, FaCT++ reasoning, Manchester syntax, Visualisation. Additionally, EMMOntoPy contains tools such as `ontoconvert`, `ontograph`, `emmocheck`, and `excel2onto`.

8. Conclusion

This report presented the validation results of the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology, a lightweight ontology development framework. The validation primarily involves surveying LOT users to assess its practical utility and impact in real-world scenarios. The survey comprises five sections, covering aspects such as participants' backgrounds and LOT's core activities. To conduct the survey, OntoCommons demonstrators were contacted. The objectives were to evaluate LOT's effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. Seven responses were collected, providing valuable feedback. The report presented a comprehensive analysis of the survey responses, including insights from open-ended questions and trends observed across participants' choices in closed-ended questions. It aims to shed light on the framework's strengths and areas for enhancement. Moreover, the OntoCommons project has improved the LOT methodology to enhance interoperability. These enhancements resulted from collaboration with diverse communities, including industry, academia, and consortia. Specifically, the LOT4OCES methodology has been developed to standardise ontology development within and beyond OntoCommons, offering important customisations and recommendations.

9. Appendix A (Questionnaire)

OntoCommons 4.7: Validation of LOT Methodology

In the context of OntoCommons task T4.3, the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology is supposed to be analysed with regard to its validity. This questionnaire is distributed to users of the LOT methodology to collect their experiences. The form consists of 5 sections. The first section gathers general information about the context in which the LOT methodology has been used. The remaining four sections correspond to each of the 4 LOT activities "Ontology Requirements Specification", "Ontology Implementation", "Ontology Evaluation", and "Ontology Maintenance".

The LOT methodology is

an agile and iterative ontology development methodology that includes four activities:

- 1) ontology requirements specification: to identify what is needed to be represented in the ontology
- 2) ontology implementation: to defined the ontology structure, elements, at a conceptual level but also encode it. This step includes also the evaluation.
- 3) ontology publication: to make thee ontology available for others
- 4) ontology maintenance: to keep the ontology updated and polished.

The figure below shows an overview of the processes that must be performed, the involved roles and the product

that results from them

For more information check the LOT website <https://lot.linkeddata.es/> and the Open Access paper <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104755>

Note that each phase is divided into more specific activities (detailed workflow <https://lot.linkeddata.es/resources/images/workflow-complete.png>)

LOT methodology main phases

1. Which of the followings best describe your user group?

Mark only one option

- OntoCommons demonstrator pilot
- project owner
- training participant at innovative prototyping
- Ontology developer (not related to OntoCommons)
- Other:
-

2. Context in OntoCommons

Please describe the context in which you used the LOT methodology in a few words. Please provide details about involved demonstrators, goals, relevant OntoCommons tasks, deliverables, and workshops.

If not applicable type "N/A"

3. *Reason for using LOT methodology*

Were you required to use the LOT methodology according to the Grant Agreement of OntoCommons? If not, please provide details about your decision to use the LOT methodology.

4. *LOT methodology training*

Did you receive training to use the LOT methodology? If so, please provide details.

5. *LOT methodology materials*

What documents did you use to follow the LOT methodology? Please provide references or links to online resources.

6. *Please tick all activities that you followed according to the LOT methodology. Also tick activities that you only followed partially.*

Select all applicable.

- Ontology Requirements Specification
- Ontology Implementation
- Ontology Publication
- Ontology Evaluation

LOT Activity: Ontology Requirements Specification

In this section, you are asked to provide details about the subactivities involved in the "Ontology Requirements Specification" activity of the LOT methodology. If a given subactivity was not followed, please write "Not applicable" or explain why the LOT methodology was not followed.

7. *Use Case Specification*

Please provide details about how the LOT methodology was used to specify use cases. If possible, please provide any produced use case specification.

8. *Data Exchange Identification*

Please provide details about how the LOT methodology was used to produce documents and other resources that have been provided to the ontology development team for the purpose of ontology engineering activities.

9. *Purpose and Scope Identification*

Please provide details about how the LOT methodology was used to specify the purpose and scope of the developed ontology.

10. *Functional Ontology Requirements*

Please provide details about the process of specifying ontology requirements. In particular, please explain whether a distributed versioning control system, e.g., GitHub, was used.

Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSD)

If possible, please share the latest version of the ORSD.

11. *Functional Ontology Requirements Formalisation*

Please provide details about any attempts to formalise ontology requirements in terms of executable test cases.

Ontology Implementation

In this section, you are asked to provide details about

the subactivities involved in the "Ontology Implementation" activity of the LOT methodology. If a given subactivity

was not followed, please write "Not applicable" or explain why the LOT methodology was not followed.

12. *Ontology Conceptualisation*

Please provide details about the creation of a conceptual model for the developed ontology. If possible, please share any created artefacts, e.g., UML diagrams.

13. *Ontology Encoding*

Please provide details about the choice of a formal knowledge representation language and its use to encode the developed conceptual model. If possible, please share the latest version of the developed ontology.

14. *Ontology Reuse*

Please provide details about whether any existing ontologies have been reused and if so, how this reuse influenced the design of the developed ontology.

Ontology Evaluation

Please provide details about what kind of quality control process have been implemented to ensure that the ontology meets any formulated requirements.

Ontology Publication

In this section, you are asked to provide details about

the subactivities involved in the "Ontology Publication" activity of the LOT methodology. If a given subactivity

was not followed, please write "Not applicable" or explain why the LOT methodology was not followed.

15. *Documentation Generation*

Please provide details about what kind of materials have been made available for the developed ontology. In particular, please comment on whether

- FAIR practices have been followed,
- there exist an HTML description of the ontology,
- metadata was added to any available resources,
- there exist a graphical representation of the ontology,
- provided materials are dependent on specific serialisations of the ontology.

16. *Online Publication*

Please provide details about whether the developed ontology has been published online in machine-readable formats as well as formats that are more appropriate for human consumption.

Ontology Maintenance

In this section, you are asked to provide details about

the sub-activities involved in the "Ontology Maintenance" activity of the LOT methodology.

If a given sub-activity

was not followed, please write "Not applicable" or explain why the LOT methodology was not followed.

17. *Bug Detection*

Please provide details about how users, developers, or domain experts can detect and report potential bugs in the ontology.

10. Appendix B (LOT4OCES related templates)

Table 1: Roles in ontology development team

LOT	Role	Responsibility	Required skill	Assigned to
Ontology User	Product owner	To provide a clear vision of the purpose and scope of the ontology, to represent both the customer and end-users, to facilitate communication between the ontology development team and the customer	Decision-making, problem-solving, storytelling, creativity, application knowledge	Use case specification, Data exchange identification, Purpose and scope identification, Functional ontology requirement completion, ontology evaluation, Bug detection, New Requirement
	Information Technology Manager	To provide information on legacy data structures, API specifications, and data exchanges.	Software development, data management, knowledge on the customer's data, software and APIs.	Data exchange identification
Domain Expert	Domain Expert	To provide general knowledge about the domain of the ontology, to supply the ontology development team with definitions of concepts specific to the target domain or application, and to provide definitions and explanations of concepts from existing standards, corpus, and other ontologies.	Domain knowledge, subject-matter expertise, awareness of relevant standards, corpus, and related ontologies for the target domain	Functional ontology requirements proposal, Functional ontology requirement completion, Ontology conceptualisation, ontology evaluation
	Ontology Analyst	To translate business needs into ontology	Ontology requirement	Use case specification,

		requirements, to ensure proper documentation of requirements, to define the scope and prioritise development, to verify that requirements are satisfied by proper testing of the ontology	engineering, critical thinking, negotiation skills, interpersonal skills	Data exchange identification, Purpose and scope identification, Functional ontology requirement specification, ORSD formalisation, Ontology documentation, Bug detection
Ontology Developer	Ontologist	To extract concepts from the requirement, to build conceptualisation of the ontology, to build definitions of concepts, to ensure that the ontology is semantically meaningful, to help in mapping concepts from different ontologies	Knowledge of different ontological and metaphysical theories, knowledge of different ontological commitments, Expertise in one or more top-level ontologies, and mid-level ontology, expertise in developing taxonomy, partonomy, and ontology	Ontology requirement specification, Ontology conceptualisation, Ontology reuse, Ontology evaluation
	Logician	To write axioms by translating definitions of ontology concepts in some formal logic system, e.g., FOL, OWL 2.0, to ensure logical consistency of the ontology through the use of reasoners and provers, to provide mappings between concepts from different ontologies	Expertise in writing axioms in some logic systems, knowledge of formal logic, and model-theoretic systems, skilled in using provers and reasoners and debugging.	Ontology conceptualisation, Ontology reuse, Ontology encoding, Ontology evaluation
	Ontology Developer	To generate the ontology artefact, e.g.,	Knowledge of ontology languages,	Ontology encoding,

		OWL/RDF file, to manage import and IRIs, to annotate the ontology, to provide metadata, to generate documentation of the ontology, to manage changes and releases of the ontology artefact.	encoding formats, proficiency in using ontology editing, documentation, and source control tools, knowledge of standard metadata properties	ontology documentation, Ontology release candidate,
	Ontology Tester	To create test cases for the ontology, to write necessary queries or set testing tools for functional testing, to measure the ontology using various metrics, to facilitate the peer-review process, to write test reports	Proficiency in creating test cases, writing queries, and using ontology evaluation tools, knowledge of various ontology metrics and their interpretation	Ontology evaluation
	Ontology Reviewer	To review and comment on the model and documentation of the ontology. To evaluate the quality of the ontology for aspects which cannot be automated. To write critiques of definitions and documentation.	Similar skills of ontologist, logician, and domain expert. Multiple reviewers should be recruited from outside the project.	Ontology Evaluation, Ontology Maintenance
	Ontology Curator	To catalogue the ontology in a suitable ontology repository, to generate accurate and sufficient FAIR metadata for the ontology, to measure and improve the FAIRness of the ontology, to manage versions of the ontology	Proficient in using ontology repository, expertise in FAIR metadata management, knowledge of FAIRness evaluation of ontology	Ontology Publication
	Data Modeler	To create data transformation, e.g., ETL, strategy, to create mappings from data sources to ontology, to set knowledge graph	Proficiency in various data transformation and mapping languages and tools, knowledge in data	

		database (KGDB) and data pipelines, to validate data represented as KG, create query APIs for the downstream use of data	life cycle management, expertise in data verification and validation, and experience with various KGDB and related ETL tools.	
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Table 2: Template for use case specification

Use Case Specification - <identifier/name>	
Introduction: (<i>Short description of the use case</i>)	
Use case owner:	(<i>Short description of the use case</i>)
Involved partners:	(<i>Product owner / Customer / Client / Vendor / Supplier / knowledge scientist/engineer / material scientist</i>)
Purpose of ontology application	(<i>Data model / data structuring / Data sharing / Overview and visualisation / Context bridging in digital communication / Software customisation / Artificial Intelligence / Service extension / Business planning / communication / Decision System / Innovation Project Workflow / QA/QC / Guided AI / Data Parsing / Data Integration Interoperability / Others</i>)
Data sources used:	(<i>Mention what data describe; source of data, e.g., database, API, diagram, text; format of data, e.g., csv, tsv, xml, json, text</i>)
Ontologies considered:	(<i>Mention if any existing ontology is used</i>)
Main Challenges:	(<i>Main challenges that the clients are facing in the current scenario</i>)
Description:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Context of the use case: (<i>Describe the context in which the use case takes place, e.g., acquiring leads in a marketing campaign, material handling in an assembly line</i>) 2) What are the pre-conditions of your use case? (<i>Describe the states of the system and environment before the use case scenario starts</i>) 3) What are the post-conditions of your use case? (<i>Describe the states of the system and environment after the use case scenario ends</i>) 4) Who are the actors involved? (<i>List of all actors mentioned in the scenario steps</i>) 	

- 5) What are the steps of the main scenario?
(Please add here a picture that describes the aforementioned user story, in a compact way with discrete steps, e.g., workflow. An additional picture in the form of a use case UML diagram with connections to actors and software/hardware components would also be helpful.)
- 6) Which data sources are used? *(Please cross-reference with the steps of the main scenario)*
- 7) What are the major (expected) contributions of this project to the use case? *(Describe how the project's outcome will mitigate the challenges of this use case)*
- 8) Name the most important 20 terms for the domain of your use case. *(If available, please add any diagrams illustrating these terms (e.g., UML diagram, ER diagram)*

Implementation plan:

(Provide a rough time plan for your implementation. Particularly, list the milestones or scenario steps - by when what will be developed. Mention any additional resources that will be available during the project and associated constraints. Include any policy or protocol that the customer wants to follow.)

FAIR plan:

- 1) Is there any existing plan for FAIRness? *(Does the customer have an existing FAIRness strategy)*
- 2) What are the future steps to improve FAIRness? *(What does the demonstrator want to improve? If there are no/little improvements made and/or foreseen, motivate why. If there is an interest in progress here, what are the roadblocks?)*

Technology readiness level: *(Follow the guides¹² for assigning TRLs)*

- 1) of different scenario steps
- 2) of the application of ontology
- 3) of different tools involved

Key Performance Indicators (KPI): *(Provide the KPIs, corresponding metrics, and expected improvement by the end of the project)*

KPI	Metric	Current	Future

¹ Mitchell, J.A., Measuring the Maturity of a Technology: Guidance on Assigning a TRL, SAND2007-6733, Sandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque, NM, October 2007.

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level

Table 3: Template for collecting data exchange specification

DATA SET/Data Exchange Format n. # – <title of the data set> Owner(s): <organisation>	
1. DATA SUMMARY	Purpose of the Data*
	Type and Format of data*
	Reused-Data
	Data origin
	Data size / Data exchange frequency
	Data security and storage
	Discoverability of data or API specification (metadata)
	Use case #
2. DATA STRUCTURE	Name of columns or fields or objects
	Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies
	Identifiability of data/transaction or primary and foreign key
	Naming conventions used
	Data model/schema/entity-relation diagram
3. DATA ACCESS	Database/repository/folder path/URI
	Sample queries
	Methods or SW tools for data access
	SW documentation and other information needed
	Join conditions, filters, aggregation
	Search keywords approach
4. DATA AVAILABILITY	Timing of data availability (incl. indications on embargo)
	Data update cycle
	Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)
	Restrictions to data use/Access control
	Expiration date
5. DATA OWNERSHIP	Data owner
	Data manager

Table 4: Template for collecting ontology functional requirement in the form of competency questions

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Question	Answer	Status	Higher level Question	Rationale	Comments	Extracted from (provenance)	Priority
Code (domain+id)	Code or label the sprint	An interrogative sentence	Number, Token, sub-sentences, or a complete sentence	Proposed, Accepted, Rejected, Pending, Deprecated	Code	Text	Text	Source of the collected CQ	High, medium, or low

Identifier: The requirement identifier needs to be unique for each requirement. A suitable naming convention needs to be decided by the project members, e.g., use case # + index, domain + index, application + index.

Sprint: The sprint of the requirement iteration. Multiple iterations may be undertaken at the beginning of the project. Separate sprints needs to be undertaken for new amendment to the purpose and scope of the use case as well as an update of the ontology.

Competency Question: The competency question.

Answer: The answer to the competency question.

Status: The status of the requirement might be: 1) proposed, 2) accepted, 3) rejected, 4) ongoing or 5) deprecated.

Higher Level Question: The # of competency questions that depend on the answer to this competency question to be answered.

Rationale: How the answer to the question is used to answer the higher-level question, e.g., provides constraints (structural, functional, quantitative, qualitative, spatial, temporal, causal etc.), provides data (create new instance, asserts new relation, record measurement etc.), provides assumptions (create new situation, initiation of process, new activity etc.).

Comment: Free text for keeping notes regarding the competency question.

Provenance: The provenance of the provided requirement (use case, interview, mail, etc.).

Priority: The priority of the requirement can be: 1) high, 2) medium, or 3) low.

Table 5: Template for pre-glossary terms

#	Term	Definition	CQ (comma-separated)	Identifiers	Synonym	Hyponym	Meronym

#: Index of the terms.

Term: Single word or a phrase

Definition: The definition of the word that corresponds to the meaning in which the term is used in the corresponding competency questions. If the same term is used with different meanings in some competency questions then they should be enlisted with different indexes.

CQ identifiers: The list of CQs from which the term is extracted (separated by a comma).

Synonym: The words or phrases that mean exactly or nearly the same as the term (separated by a comma).

Hyponym (optional): The words or phrases with broader meaning (superordinate or supertype) of the term if available.

Meronym (optional): The words or phrases which correspond to the part of the entity defined by the term if available.

Table 6: Template for conceptualising ontology term

NEW TERM NAME

(use the preferred label, or IRI name, provided in the first table as title)

General Concept Info:

IRI:	Suggested entity new IRI.
OWL Type:	Class ObjectProperty Individual
Concept Elucidation:	Natural language definition of the concept (elucidation). Here the concept that we want to introduce is expressed as precisely as possible, making references to knowledge domain resources, including instance and usage examples when relevant. The necessary and sufficient conditions for the definition can be found by applying trait analysis. Follow the 'best practice for definition' while writing the definition.
Labels:	Labels used to address the concept, ordered as: i) preferred (one) (the label to primarily used to shortly refer to the concept) ii) alternative (multiple) (labels that are commonly used to address the concept in practice, even if they are used with narrower or wider sense) iii) deprecated (multiple) (labels that are misleading with respect to the concept, because of misuse, ambiguity or too wide meaning).

Knowledge Domain Resources:

Related Domain Resources:	Existing domain resources (e.g. standards, books, articles, dictionaries) that defines or are related to the concept (provide reference to the resource and quote the relevant informational content). More than one resource can be reported. These resources are aimed to support the choice of the above concept choice and elucidation.
Comments:	Explain the motivations behind the concept definition with reference to the domain resources, underlying similarities and differences.

Trait analysis:

Traits	List of all possible traits for the term
Analysis	Trait analysis table and rationales

Alignments To Existing Ontologies: (1: vertical, TLOs; 2: horizontal, MLOs)
1: Vertical Alignments

Target Ontology:	Existing IRI of the ontology that will express the concept according to its logical framework (concept alignment).
Related Ontology Entities:	List of terms and IRIs of the Target Ontology entities that are relevant for the concept (documentation is supposed to be accessible through the target ontology).
Mapping Elucidation:	Natural language description of the mapping choice and motivations.
Semantic Relation Level:	The level of semantic relationship between the Concept and the Target Ontology entities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equivalence (strong mapping) (e.g. owl:equivalentClass, owl:equivalentProperty) • Strong Hierarchical (e.g. rdfs:subClassOf, rdfs:subPropertyOf) • Weak Hierarchical (e.g. skos:narrower, skos:broader) • Similarity (e.g. skos:related). It should be noted that owl mapping properties are applicable to classes and properties whereas SKOS mapping properties are applicable to instances. Users should be careful in using them interchangeably.
Mapping Axioms:	Proposed mapping axiom (or axioms) between the Concept entity and the Target Ontology entities in a OWL2 compliant syntax (e.g. Turtle, Manchester, RDF/XML, Functional-Style, OWL/XML).

EXISTENT CONCEPT NAME (optional)

(use the preferred label, or IRI name, provided in the first table as title)

General Concept Info:

IRI:	Entity IRI
OWL Type:	Class ObjectProperty Individual
Concept Elucidation:	Refer to ontology annotations or other existing OFFICIAL documentation that defines the concept in natural language.
Labels:	Labels (e.g. rdfs:label) used to address the concept, ordered as i) preferred (one), ii) alternative, iii) deprecated.

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